

METHODS OF TEACHING WRITING SKILLS TO STUDENTS OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article examines the growing role of written communication in the modern globalized world. Skills in this area are increasingly acquiring the status of the most demanded both in the educational and professional spheres. The rapid growth in the volume and pace of information exchange via the Internet and the worldwide trend towards written knowledge testing have brought written communication to the fore. In this regard, the training of future linguists-teachers of written foreign language is of particular importance for the system of higher linguistic education.

Key words: written speech, linguodidactics, professional contact, speaking and writing, foreign language written communication, computer programs.

I. Introduction

Currently, teachers of a foreign language at school and university face a number of very important problems for the development of general pedagogy and linguodidactics. Among them, a significant place is occupied by one that was not previously given importance either in the scientific or in the pedagogical environment [11]. We are talking about learning the skills of foreign language writing.

Teaching a foreign language is aimed at developing foreign language communicative competence among students, it involves achieving a level that allows future specialists to solve professional problems in oral and written speech activity [2]. Teaching types of foreign language speech activity (reading, listening, speaking and writing) is implemented in close relationship, providing a solution to the problem: extracting information when reading and listening to texts of a professional nature, understanding and comprehension, and further speech production, implemented in speaking and writing, including analysis and structuring the received data [10].

The rapid increase in the volume and pace of information exchange, the accelerated development of computer communications, the main tool for professional contacts, brought written communication to the fore. With a certain importance and value of oral learning, today almost 80% of information exchange in the field of science, engineering and technology, both within legal organizations and between them, is carried out through telecommunications, namely in writing [9]. Foreign language written communication, in particular, in the global Internet is necessary for all students and all specialties. During the period of study, its importance as a tool for accessing sources of information and, therefore, education is undeniable. On the other hand, professional written communication in a foreign language using electronic means of communication has become an integral part of the activities of any institution - scientific or industrial. The lack of skills and abilities of

productive written speech leads to self-doubt of specialists, to failures in work and, in the end, to financial losses.

II. Materials

The problem and issues of teaching foreign language written speech were considered in the works of many foreign and domestic scientists and practitioners. The most profound methodological side of this problem was studied in the works of G.F. Demidenko, T.M. Enalieva, Ya.M. Kolker, J.I.K. Mazunova, R.P. Milruda, A.A. Mirolyubova and others. The works of such scientists as N.I. Zhinkin, J.I.P. Zinder, A.R. Luria and others [6].

- teaching foreign language writing in secondary school;
- learning to write.

A number of studies have been carried out that consider the teaching of foreign language writing in the framework of professional language education at the initial and advanced stages in postgraduate education, within the framework of communicative competence, in the context of speech science, using a printed manual and computer programs, from the standpoint of the adequacy of the expression of a communicative statement, etc. (V. F. Govorova, O. A. Dolgina, J. L. B. Kaplich, N. N. Kondakova, O. V. Kudryashova, L. G. Kuzmina, N. M. Petrenko, J. I. V. Sabanova, I. N. Tutatchikova, T.V. Khilchenko and others). The work of L.P. Tarnaeva, which addresses the issues of teaching written language in the context of the dialogue of cultures [5].

III. Results

The writing skill serves educational activity, therefore, teaching students to write is one of the priorities along with the formation of reading and counting skills. The task of schools is not only to teach students to write, that is, to master the graphic system of the language and be able to translate sounds into letters, but to teach them to write beautifully and quickly [1].

Teachers know that, despite their apparent simplicity, the methods of writing lessons do not bring the expected results. 90% of the difficulties students experience are related to learning to write. 25-30% of these difficulties are permanent.

There are many reasons, they can be divided into two groups.

1. Students' difficulties have internal and external causes: insufficiently developed visual memory, deficiencies in visual-motor coordination, visuo-spatial perception, difficulties in sound-letter analysis, phonemic perception, difficulties in concentration.

2. Teacher difficulties: insufficient qualifications of the teacher, inconsistency of teaching methods with the age and functional abilities of children, lack of alternative methods, teaching approaches that would take into account the child's deviations in mastering writing, inconsistency between the family and the school [7].

Psychologists refer to the process of writing as one of the most complex forms of speech activity, in which speech is fixed by tracing letters, translated from oral to graphic. The process of writing involves the cerebral cortex, the organs of hearing and vision, speech-motor organs and many muscles of the body. It is the last component of the process of writing that differs from reading. It has a complex psychophysiological structure [8].

IV. Analysis

At the same time, the analysis of the literature on the problem of writing, written language, didactic means of forming written speech, led to the conclusion about the value of these works and the undoubted importance of continuing in-depth development at the theoretical and practical levels of this issue. There is practically no complete system of didactic tools that

ensure the development of the necessary skills of writing. The formation of communicative-textual activity in the field of the ability to create a written monologue text in a foreign language remains insufficiently developed [3].

The hypothesis of our study: the development of written language of school students will be effective if:

- it is carried out taking into account the principles of the unity of theory and practice, the mediation of external influences on the subject by internal psychological conditions for the formation of the subject's personality through activity;
- a holistic and logically interconnected set of didactic tools has been created that optimizes the process of developing the skills and abilities of foreign language writing;
- development is presented as a movement of a person from one level of his formation to another, higher one, with the passage of a number of stages;
- the content of systematic, independent work of students is focused on the development of communicative skills that meet the requirements.

V. Discussion

Thus, the process of writing is very difficult for students, since it is normally carried out on the basis of sufficiently formed speech and non-speech functions. The lack of formation of any function can cause a violation of the letter. The causes of impaired reading and writing are similar. Types of errors in writing: skipping letters, rearranging letters, dropping out letters or combinations of letters, the appearance of an extra syllable or letter, underwriting a word [4].

The writing skill belongs to sensorimotor skills, but unlike other sensorimotor skills (sewing, sawing, etc.), it serves learning activities, therefore, it is difficult to form, in parallel with reading, spelling and the development of written language.

Thus, the developed pedagogical and methodological foundations for organizing the educational process for the development of foreign-language written speech among students contributed to solving the problem of identifying a set of didactic tools, implementing the tasks set in the study based on the classical structure of the educational process.

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